

EuroMix

European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures

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Report on stakeholder workshop 2

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Report on stakeholder workshop 2

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Summary

This report summarises the main outcomes from two stakeholder workshops that were held in Brussels (BE) on March 26-27, 2019, to gather key scientists, researchers, policy makers, and stakeholders from authorities, industry and civil society.

On 26 March 2019 two Horizon2020-funded projects, EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix, held a joint stakeholder workshop, entitled *The Chemical Cocktail Challenge*, at Thon Hotel EU, Brussels. The two projects have been working to address different aspects of the impacts of mixtures on human health and the environment, including potential links to research activities at the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC). Therefore, it was decided to organise the final stakeholder workshop of EuroMix jointly with EDC-MixRisk for increased impact and outreach to a broader group of stakeholders and potential multipliers.

The aim of the workshop was to highlight the main results and conclusions from the two projects, and their implications for future needs for chemical mixture risk assessment. Key results were presented and new tools and approaches for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals (mixtures) were demonstrated and how these could benefit future European food and chemical safety policy.

The workshop was organised in two joint morning sessions; (I) Joint forces tackling chemical mixtures - Key results and conclusions from EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix and (II) Stakeholder perspectives on EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix implications for the future, followed by two parallel project specific afternoon sessions; (A) Applications of the EuroMix toolbox for improving exposure assessment of mixtures, (B) EDC-MixRisk approach: Case study of mixture effects on sexual development, (C) Applications of the EuroMix toolbox for improving hazard assessment of mixtures and (D) From science to regulation- EDC-MixRisk approaches for better risk assessment and management of mixtures. Both the morning and afternoon sessions ended with general open discussions. The project specific afternoon sessions from EDC-MixRisk i.e. sessions B and D are not covered in this report, since they were focused on EDC-MixRisk results and outcomes.

Overall chairs for the joint morning sessions were Gregory Moore from Kemi and Charles Wijnker from the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport in the Netherlands. The project specific EuroMix afternoon sessions were chaired by Mirjam Luijten from the Dutch Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) RIVM and Alan Boobis from Imperial College London (ICL)..

In total, 115 participants attended the workshop, representing various stakeholder groups: academia (29%), government/authorities (24%), industry (15%), NGOs (10%) European commission (9%), policy makers (8%) and others (6%), with representation from the EU countries & associated countries (IS, NO, Swiss), USA, Canada, Israel and Japan.

The workshop programme ended with a joint dinner at Atelier 29 to celebrate the success of the two projects as well as a fruitful joint stakeholder meeting.

On 27 March 2019, EuroMix held a half day project specific stakeholder workshop that focused on the EuroMix approach and developments, entitled *Harmonisation and Usability of the EuroMix tools*, at Thon Hotel EU, Brussels.

The aim of the workshop was to present the EuroMix AOP-wise test strategy and test results, the EuroMix model and data platform, discuss how the results can be used internationally as

well as for follow-up activities on combined exposure assessment to multiple chemicals. Overall chair was Anton Rietveld from RIVM.

In total, 51 participants attended the workshop representing various stakeholder groups i.e. government/authorities (39%), industry (23,5%) academia (10%), European commission (8%), NGOs (8%), policy makers (6%) and others (6%) with representation from the EU countries and associated countries (IS, NO), Canada, Japan.

The entire programmes from both workshops are presented in Appendix 1. This report contains the abstracts provided by the speakers, questions raised by the audience for clarification and the answers provided by the speakers after each presentation as well as the questions and answers from the general open discussions held at the end of the sessions (excluding the project specific EDC-MixRisk sessions B and D).

The presentations given during the joint morning session and the EuroMix project specific sessions can be found on the EuroMix website

(<http://www.euromixproject.eu/2019/04/08/stakeholder-workshops-26-27-march-2019-presentations/>).

The Chemical Cocktail Challenge

Overall chairs: *Gregory Moore, Keml and Charles Wijnker, Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport*

Overall rapporteurs: *Helga Gunnlaugsdóttir, MATIS and Elina Drakvik, KI*

Session 1 - Joint forces tackling chemical mixtures - Key results and conclusions from EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix

Rapporteurs: *Sophie Jensen, MATIS and Mattias Öberg, KI*

Welcome from the project coordinator(s) and aims of the workshop

Åke Bergman coordinator of the EDC-MixRisk project and Jacob v. Klaveren coordinator from the EuroMix project welcomed the 115 participants attending the workshop,

Mixtures and food safety

Sabine Julicher, Director, Food and Feed Safety, Innovation, DG Sante, EC

Progress through collaboration is essential to address not only the regulatory requirements, but also the growing concerns of consumers and stakeholders regarding exposure to chemical mixtures. The Commission is committed to move ahead in this important area with the final goal of an integrated approach for assessing exposure to chemical mixtures in all relevant areas. Both the EDC-MixRisk and the EuroMix projects mark significant breakthroughs in our understanding of human daily exposure to chemical mixtures, their role is prominent in providing information for future risk management decisions on the safety of chemicals in mixtures.

The methodology for assessing human exposure to mixtures of chemicals remains a challenge. In the field of pesticides residues, efforts for developing an appropriate methodology for the assessment of the risks from multiple residues have been going for more than a decade. The ongoing evaluation to check whether the EU pesticides legislation is still 'fit for purpose' highlighted the need for increased efforts in addressing the cumulative and synergistic effects of pesticide residues. Towards this end, DG SANTE is closely cooperating with the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and Member States on the development of an EU-harmonised approach for assessing the risk of the dietary cumulative exposure to multiple pesticide residues.

No clarification questions

How research contributes to solving the mixture challenge

Maria Pilar Aguar Fernandez, Head of Unit, DG RTD, EC

My opening statement, on behalf of the European Commission's DG Research & Innovation, which is funding through Horizon 2020 the two projects, EDC-MIXRISK and EuroMix, will highlight some of the achievements of the two projects. Furthermore, I will present some of the past and present policy initiatives such as those related to endocrine disruptors or mixture toxicity that have been the guiding forces behind to drive research forward. Finally, I will briefly describe relevant features from the proposed new Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe.

No clarification questions

EuroMix highlights and key recommendations

Jacob v. Klaveren, RIVM; Alfonso Lampen, BfR and Hilko van der Voet, WUR

We still don't know much about the consequences of exposure to chemical mixtures. Research under the EuroMix project will help stakeholders closing the gap. EuroMix aimed to establish novel testing and assessment strategies for chemical mixtures, to develop appropriate mixture risk assessment methodology and to implement this in a well-accessible inter-operational data and model platform.

Human biomonitoring studies show that people have a considerable number of man-made chemicals in their bodies, and European regulations stipulate the need to consider the potential mixture effect. However, animal testing should be reduced, and new testing methods are required. For the EuroMix team, the question was simple: How do we translate these good intentions to effective actions?

The team delivered a test strategy to generate missing toxicity data needed for future risk assessments. They tested many chemicals and ran several case studies with a large number of chemicals affecting three adverse outcomes; liver steatosis, skeletal malformation and endocrine disruption. They also developed a novel risk modelling approach aligned with needs in Europe and elsewhere.

The approach starts with *in silico* modelling grouping chemicals into cumulative assessment groups. Then *in vitro* assays are used to investigate the appropriateness of the dose addition assumption and to derive the relative toxicity of chemicals. Results from *in-vitro* testing are then compared with data from animal studies. Although *in-vitro* assays already allow generation of new hazard data on yet-untested chemicals, their results need to be extrapolated from internal exposure concentrations to external doses before being used in mixture risk assessment. For *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) substance-specific kinetic models have been developed.

EuroMix has delivered an open web-based data and model platform for exposure, hazard and risk assessment. The modular system includes *in silico* modelling, dose-response modelling of *in vitro* test and *in vivo* results, the derivation of relative potency factors, an IVIVE modelling approach and the combination of hazard characterisations with dietary and non-dietary exposure assessments into margins of exposure. Eleven European Member States performed dietary exposure assessments using EuroMix data and models. Case studies addressing multiple exposure routes of bisphenols and pesticides, a comparison with human biomonitoring data and a feasibility study on simultaneous exposure to pesticides, additives and contaminants regulated under different regulatory sectors will be further explored. Stakeholders have been successfully trained on the EuroMix models.

For better or worse, chemicals have become an integrant part of our lives. And while there is still much we don't know about the consequences of this ubiquity on our health, EuroMix is certainly making headway. A EuroMix follow-up initiative, as part of the EFSA Risk Assessment Agenda, is currently under discussion aiming to apply the EuroMix test approach and risk models to other toxic endpoints and/or relevant combination of chemicals.

Questions for clarification:

Q (Industry representative): Technical question regarding relative potency. If there is data, what would be the benefit of *in vitro* + *in vivo* data? Would it be more relative to humans?

- A** (EuroMix representative): The way EuroMix used in vivo data and the in-vitro-to-in-vivo extrapolation should be seen as a proof-of-principle. We need to build up experience of how the in vitro data can be used optimal in mixture risk assessment. It is also recognised that using in vivo data is either optimal because of lacking dose-response data and information on the mode of action. It depends on future Regulation and further experience whether alternative testing will be accepted in the regulatory context. This should also be seen in the context of OECD guidance on test strategies.

EDC-MixRisk highlights and key messages

Åke Bergman, KI; Carl-Gustaf Bornehag, KU; Joëlle Rüegg, KI and Chris Gennings, ICAHN

A healthy endocrine system is essential for our ability to reproduce and develop. Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are linked to serious health problems such as diabetes, obesity, neurodevelopmental disorders and reproductive problems. The fact that we are exposed to complex mixtures of EDCs is of particular concern. EDC-MixRisk is an EU Horizon 2020 research project that has developed a novel whole mixture approach that is based on 1) identifying EDCs in mixtures (so called bad actors) associated with adverse health outcomes in epidemiological studies, 2) preparing artificial mixtures of the bad actors and testing them in different experimental settings, and 3) using the experimental data for mixture risk assessment. This proof-of-concept will enable more systematic integration of epidemiological and experimental evidence into mixture risk assessment strategies. In our presentation, we will highlight the key results and conclusions of this project and how they compare to other testing and risk assessment approaches. We will also present the future needs identified based on the EDC-MixRisk outcome.

[Session 2 - Stakeholder perspectives on EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix implications for the future](#)

Chairs: Gregory Moore, Keml and Charles Wijnker, Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

Rapporteurs: Helene Deruwe, Freshfel and Elina Drakvik, KI

EFSA's perspective

Jean-Lou Dorne, EFSA

The scientific Committee of EFSA has recently adopted after public consultation a guidance document on harmonised risk assessment methods of combined exposure to multiple chemicals "chemical mixtures" for human health, animal health and ecological risk assessment. EFSA is currently implementing these methods in the areas of human and animal health for regulated compounds (i.e. pesticides), feed additives and contaminants as well as in the ecological area particularly for bee health. In parallel, EFSA is developing a set of open source tools and models to support biologically-based risk assessment of mixtures.

The Horizon 2020 projects EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix have investigated the impact of chemical mixtures on human health particularly for pesticides and contaminants. The approach taken for EDC-MixRisk included experimental testing strategies such as in vivo, in vitro and in silico methods for

endocrine disruptors and epidemiological studies in an integrated manner while also considering health risks and societal impact. The Euro Mix project has developed in vivo, in vitro and in silico methods and integrated all results and models in a toolbox to support human exposure, hazard and risk assessment of mixtures using component-based approaches. Considerations of these research activities from an EFSA perspective are given with regards to methodologies and human risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple pesticides and contaminants.

OECD's perspective

Eva Leinala, OECD

The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) recently published a document on Considerations for Assessing Combined Exposures to Multiple Chemicals. The approaches in both EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix align with these considerations. The OECD also works to advance the use of in silico and in vitro methods, inclusion of mechanistic thinking (e.g. use of Adverse Outcome Pathways) and Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment that also apply new approach methodologies. The two H2020 initiatives provide examples of how to combine various types of data to build a case for the need for and support the results of assessment of risk to combined exposures. Linking epidemiological or in vivo results to in vitro approaches, harnessing biomonitoring and use data to inform co-exposure, examining modelling information in the context of measured data, building grouping rationales based on mechanistic thinking.

Reflecting on discussions at the OECD, the main risk assessment methods are in place for assessment of mixtures, however there is a need for further examples of the use of these methods in different information contexts. Also, for the uptake of new methods (e.g. new in vitro methods), there is a clear expression from regulators for transparency and clarity on what information new methods are providing, their domain of applicability and the interpretation of results. Tools are available to aid in a transition between research and regulatory use.

ChemTrust's perspective

Ninja Reineke, ChemTrust

No abstract was received from this speaker.

Industry perspective

Steffen Schneider, BASF

No abstract was received from this speaker.

Perspectives from three European Commission's DG's

Laura Fabrizi, DG SANTE; Peter Korytar, DG ENV and Stephanie Bopp, DG JRC

The European Commission has worked in the area of chemical mixtures over the last decade (The State-of-the-Art report on Chemical Mixtures (2009), the Opinion of the non-food Scientific Committees (2011) and the Commission Communication on Chemical Mixtures (2012)). The Communication identified data and knowledge gaps and called for an improved understanding of the exposure to chemical mixtures, the toxic effects, modes of action and potential interactions of chemicals, as well as identification of specific mixtures to be addressed with priority. It also called for follow up actions by Horizon 2020 projects.

On endocrine disruptors, the European Union legislation foresees strict regulatory measures to protect the human health and the environment: they are identified and regulated under REACH Regulation and regulatory criteria for their identification in the sector of biocides and pesticides were adopted for the 1st time worldwide, including scientific guidance for their implementation. The Communication "Towards a comprehensive EU framework on endocrine disruptors (2018)" presents a strategy to address endocrine disruptors comprehensively and acknowledges data gaps in understanding combined exposure to those and other substances.

Both projects, EuroMix and EDC-MixRisk contributed to fill some of these gaps by providing a toolbox for exposure, hazard and risk assessment, making progress on integration of epidemiological and experimental data for improved strategies for mixture risk assessment, considering societal impact. The link of the projects with ongoing initiatives in pesticide cumulative risk assessment, endocrine disruptors and overall methodology to address chemical mixtures will be discussed from a policy related perspective.

Open discussion

- Q** (NGO representative): For EuroMix: Can the tests that were being done on e.g. zebrafish be used for the identification of neurodevelopmental toxicity of chemicals or chemical mixtures and could that be used and merged with your work? For EDC-MixRisk: Can AOPs be helpful to group pesticides and identify common toxicity pathways of pesticides that then could be used to better understand the uncertainties.
- A** (EuroMix representative): The strategy is here to identify tests that could help to generate the missing data from the toxicology part. Zebra fish can be used for many endpoints. The acceptance of tests should be placed in the perspective of OECD guidance on alternative test strategies. EuroMix delivered the proof of principle. The advice of EuroMix is to make these tests available, to have them used aiming to generating missing data for mixture risk assessment. Future acceptance of tests and/or mixture risk assessment is a policy decision and not a responsibility of the EuroMix project. The EuroMix model and data platform is a tool that can facilitate the discussion, this can be used in a neutral form. The users stakeholders need to decide how to use the tool in practice, it offers flexibility of conservative and less conservative approaches.
- A** (EDC-MixRisk representative): AOP concept is useful to better understanding the biological process and how chemicals might initiate a cellular process converging to an adverse outcome. However, it is very challenging to start identifying all the possible MIEs which are now required for a full blown AOP.

- A** (EDC-MixRisk representative): AOPs are interesting to better understand the hazard assessment, but there is the complex issue of exposure. For endocrine disturbing chemicals exposure is much broader than exposure to pesticides only. There is an enormous number of different chemicals with different endpoints. The pesticide conversation is just a part of it. Here we need to break the borders between the different types of chemicals as long as they end up in human body or in wildlife.
- Q** (Industry representative): Regarding agrochemicals, and in particular endocrine disruptors: there is an obligation to submit ED data either using in vitro and/or in vivo ED tests, otherwise the chemical won't be registered. EuroMix made enormous progress on certain AOPs. Some of the tests could really help to reduce animal testing, but how are we going to validate the in vitro tests? What will be next in terms of in vitro testing and its validation?
- A** (EuroMix representative): We set a proof of principle, e.g. for in vitro and in vivo testing for liver toxicity. A mixture study was done, where mixtures were combined in vitro. Next steps: in human liver cells (comparable to liver cells in rat) and mixture the tests performed in, zebra fish, thereafter verification of in vitro assessment with other species. Main goal is to get the proof of principle. PBK modelling or IVIVE modelling approaches is the connection point between in vitro and in vivo.
- A** (EFSA representative): The new data requirement for kinetics and comparative metabolism between rats and tuna is probably an opportunity to study the consequence of metabolism toxicity.
- A** (EuroMix representative): Euromix performed kinetic modelling, but this certainly needs improvement and continuation before in vitro test can be accepted and used in regulatory frameworks. On the other hand we need to realise that the hazard data from the current animal or in vivo testing is far from perfect. Although animal currently is set as the golden standard there are major limitation in a lack of dose response data from these studies.
- Q** (Industry representative): question to the risk managers: It is difficult to come up with risk management decisions. How to manage the risk? Are we dealing with the oldest or the most potent compound first to be banned? Are we looking for risk drivers? How is it organised
- A** (Policy maker representative): EFSA concluded cumulative risk assessment for pesticide assuming dose addition. The results were discussed with risk managers and guided problem formulation (e.g. the questions the Commission is raising). The new risk assessment based on the problem formulation and new data needs careful considerations before it can be used in the risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple pesticides. The Commission's plan is to have a step-based approach, starting to use the mixture risk assessment methodology for pesticides initially in the EFSA annual reports (as of 2020) on monitoring results of pesticide residues. This work can start using the first cumulative assessment groups which have been developed by EFSA. In parallel the Commission might consider a prospective scenario addressing the safety of the new pesticides to be authorised considering the mixture effect of the pesticide already on the market as a background exposure.
- A** (EDC-MixRisk representative): Start of providing a data-driven strategy for mixture assessment, based on an acceptable concentration range model.
- Q** (NGO representative): Pesticide regulation is based on the precautionary principle: it is based on the principle that they should bring no harm to humans and environment. It doesn't say 'low risk', it says 'no harm'. That's why there are cut-off criteria. It also says that pesticides shouldn't have cumulative effect, which was also mentioned in the MRL legislation, enforced

in 2005. For more than 10 years, there promises are made by EFSA and the Commission to implement mixture risk assessment, but no action is taken so far. As civil society, the question is, since there is a precautionary principle, why isn't there e.g. another extra safety factor (e.g. mixture safety factor) of 10 in place, especially for these pesticides which are designed to be toxic.

We want to promote a safer model of food production. Currently, the pesticide regulation is undergoing a refit process. Would the risk managers and policy makers use this opportunity to take action to consider the results of the EU funded projects into the refit? And will this influence other safety Regulations than only the Pesticide Regulation?

- A** (Policy maker representative): In both Pesticide and MRL Regulation it is stated that cumulative effects should be taken into account when the methodology is available. But the difficulty to develop this methodology has been underestimated. A harmonised approach doesn't exist yet, even though research is being funded. To set additional safety factors for mixtures at random is not a valuable solution. Such a factor might also be dependent on the type of mixtures. First steps are being set for pesticides.
- A** (Policy maker representative): If mixture regulation is placed in a broader context, it was indicated by the Commission that Mixtures is highlighted as an issue in evaluations of the regulations (fitness check of regulation). When new regulations will be replacing current legislation (e.g. the refit of some legislation), the topic will be taken into account. Some proactive steps are being taken, looking into how to deal with protection of water, grouping approaches. It was stressed that changing legislation is a political issue, and a political decision is therefore needed.
- A** (EDC-MixRisk representative): Other areas of risk assessment: the pharma industry and radiation industry questions the lack of regulation of chemicals. Legislation is needed there, but not in place.
- Q** (Academic representative): the two projects have different perspectives and approaches. How can these be merged? What can be the complimentary tools for each other?
- A** (EuroMix representative): there has been cooperation throughout, but European projects always need to stick to the Grant Agreement. Follow-up can be made in the future. It is combining experimental work with epidemiology, looking at alternative testing.
- A** (EuroMix representative): The connection point between the two projects is the adverse outcome pathways reasoning. The EuroMix project is more focussed on registration, while EDCMix Risk starting point is more focussed on epidemiological finding. Both project have performed tests to improve understanding of the way chemicals act mechanistically (e.g. mode of action).
- A** (EDC-MixRisk representative): Started from different starting points, but it is important to look at similarities in order to work together.
- A** (EFSA representative): Human biomonitoring is also another connection.
- Q** (DG RTD representative): What is needed in the future for the creation of a common knowledge-base?
- A** (EuroMix representative): An international risk assessment agenda with EFSA, shared by the Members States is useful. Many endpoints need further funding and more cooperation.

- A** (EDC-MixRisk representative): Time and money. There is a lot of cooperation between the projects working on mixtures. This cooperation is needed.

EuroMix session A: Applications of the EuroMix toolbox for improving exposure assessment of mixtures

Chair: *Mirjam Luijten, RIVM*

Rapporteur: *Sophie Jensen, MATIS*

Exposure assessment overarching sectors and tools to identify mixtures of concern

Amelie Crepet, ANSES

The EuroMix project has developed a strategy for mixture risk assessment. In particular, it has proposed a methodology that integrates exposures and hazard information to perform a combined exposure assessment and to identify relevant mixtures of chemicals to which the European population is exposed via food.

For a combined exposure assessment, substances were classified into cumulative assessment groups (CAGs). Relative potency factors for each substance were calculated to express exposure as toxicity-equivalents of a defined reference compound. Finally, exposures expressed as toxicity-equivalents were summed for each individual in the food consumption database and margins of exposure were calculated. The method to identify relevant mixtures consists of risk-based identification of co-occurrent substances in diet for a given time frame.

The data needed, and the developed methodology will be presented and illustrated with different case studies around the CAG liver steatosis performed with the EuromixToolBox.

Questions for clarification:

- Q** (Industry representative): Simple technical question. What determines the reference compound?
- A** (EuroMix representative): That is a big question. In theory the mathematical results are not affected by the choice of reference compound. For a toxicological point of view it is important to choose a compound with the best information also with high toxicity (including a representative set of dose levels) and the best criteria means the uncertainty is reduced.

Aggregated exposure assessment

Marc Kennedy, FERA

Populations can be exposed to chemical mixtures from one or more non-dietary sources, in addition to their dietary exposure. There is a need for general purpose tools that can quantify the combined (aggregated) mixture exposure for the affected subpopulations. The EuroMix toolbox provides a non-dietary module that can combine dietary exposures with measurements, or external model results, representing non-dietary exposures. The functionality originally developed in the EuroMix toolbox

for dietary risk assessment and mixture identification can now also be applied using the aggregated exposure sources.

Results from 3 case studies developed within the EuroMix project will be presented. These illustrate the capabilities of aggregated modelling for diverse applications, compound groups and health effects. In the following examples dietary exposures and the specified non-dietary exposures were considered jointly:

- Pesticide mixtures from incidental residential exposure due to arable crop spraying. The UK adult population is considered and information on sprayed mixtures is taken from the UK Pesticide Usage Survey
- Bisphenol mixtures in personal care products, dust and thermal paper
- Pyrethroid mixtures from air, dust, veterinary usage and medicine

Questions for clarification:

Q (Academic representative): Were natural pyrethrins included? If not, why?

A (EuroMix representative): We are looking at the general population here => no data on that. We include different sources and later choose what is the main source. But we don't have the data.

Q (NGO representative): No Bisphenols from Personal Care Products? Was there no data or is it an insignificant source?

A (EuroMix representative): This will be presented afterwards in Trine's talk.

Q (Industry representative): Regarding exposure in the 3rd case study results (pyrethrins exposure) – refined scenarios – what is that?

A (EuroMix representative): The optimistic, pessimistic and refined scenarios are terminology used in the EFSA guidance on the use of probabilistic modelling for dietary exposure to pesticide residues. In practice the pessimistic assumptions will be too pessimistic and optimistic assumptions too optimistic => the real answer is somewhere in between. The refined value is intended to represent a more realistic case.

Human study and how to compare real life exposure with predicted exposure using the EuroMix concept and toolbox.

Trine Husøy, NIPH

The Horizon 2020 EuroMix project aims to provide validated test strategies for hazard and exposure assessments of chemical mixtures. A human biomonitoring (BM) study was performed to study the exposure to chemicals present in foods and personal care products (PCPs). For two 24-hour study periods separated by 2-3 weeks, adult volunteers (44 males and 100 females) in Norway kept detailed diaries on food consumption (type/brand, weight, time and packaging material) and the usage of PCPs (type/brand of product, time and number of applications, and number of showers and hand washes). The participants also registered the number of thermal papers (TP) handled. In parallel, 24-hour urine samples were collected. Bisphenol's (BP's), parabens, triclosan (TRCS), triclocarban (TRCB) oxybenzone (OXB), imazalil and metabolites of phthalates and boscalid were measured in the urine of the first day. Concentrations (log transformed) in urine were used in a

multivariate linear regression (MLR) analysis with the main food and PCP categories. Exposure to bisphenols, BPA, BPS and BPF, from foods, PCPs, and TP was modeled for the study population. The EuroMix toolbox was used to calculate individual external exposure from foods, aggregating dietary with non-dietary exposures from PCPs and TP, and for the comparison with BM data. The good agreement between the ranges of modeled and measured BPA amounts indicates that available concentrations, especially from the main exposure source food, mirrored the exposure situation realistically, and suggests that the model structure is applicable and considers the relevant exposure sources. For BPS and BPF, modeled amounts mostly underestimated measured amounts, which suggests that the current data situation is insufficient to represent actual exposures. Overall, the participants in the EuroMix BM study were exposed to a mixture of phenols and phthalates. A variety of food categories and PCPs were found to be possible sources of these chemicals. The results from the BM study indicate a complex pattern of exposure to numerous chemicals, originating from multiple sources depending on individual diet and PCP preferences.

No clarification questions

EuroMix session C: Applications of the EuroMix toolbox for improving hazard assessment of mixtures

Chair: *Alan Boobis, ICL*

Rapporteur: *Marc Kennedy, FERA*

Lower tier assessment using *in silico* approaches

Ad Peijnenburg, WUR

In Work Package 2 of the EuroMix project an *in silico*-based workflow has been set up which is proposed to be used as a first tier in the risk assessment of chemical mixtures. The workflow consists of four steps. The first step is the identification of chemicals that are relevant for food and feed and of interest for combined exposures. In the second step, the probability that a chemical belongs to a certain Cumulative Assessment Group (CAG) is determined using QSAR and/or molecular docking models. The third step concerns the assignment of a relative potency factor (RPF) to each chemical that was considered in the previous step to be part of the CAG of interest. If exposure data are available, these relative potencies can be applied to scale the exposures of all mixture components. Conservative, worst case NOAELs as the basis for RPFs can be derived using Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) concepts. Possibly more realistic estimates of potency can be derived from the binding energies calculated by molecular docking, and ultimately NOAELs from read-across based on chemical similarity to a data-rich compound should give the most realistic estimate. Finally, in the fourth step, the mixture risk is determined by adding up all the scaled exposures of the mixture components that are predicted to be part of a CAG. The *in-silico* workflow and all the data obtained with the models for three CAG endpoints - hepatotoxicity, developmental toxicity and endocrine disruption - are implemented in the EuroMix MCRA software tool. The models in the *in-silico* mixture risk assessment workflow can also be used for prioritization and ranking for further testing, i.e. to identify the substances that contribute most to the calculated risk for a specific CAG.

No clarification questions

EuroMix test strategy: use of *in vitro* data to improve and/or complete hazard data collection for chemicals relevant for cumulative effect on AOP liver steatosis

Alfonso Lampen, BfR

The EuroMix project test strategy for steatosis is a mechanism-based strategy, using the concept of adverse outcome pathways (AOPs). An AOP describes, in a linear fashion, linkages (key events relationships) between chemically-induced adverse effects (key events, KEs) at various levels of biological organization, progressing from a molecular initiating event (MIE) to an adverse outcome (AO) that is relevant to risk assessment and regulatory decision-making. Therefore, an *in vitro* assay toolbox was developed to evaluate the role of mode of action (MoA) and key events of chemicals. The bioassay toolbox contains optimal *in vitro* assays to detect MoA for liver toxicity and maps to molecular initiating events (MIE) and key events (KE) of the AOP for steatosis. Exposure-based as well as *in silico* (QSAR) proposed substances were assessed according to this AOP-wise testing strategy.

When assessing combined exposure, it is essential to define the potency of each component (relative potency factor) which allows the appropriate testing of each compound being assessed. Therefore, relative potencies were computed by using benchmark dose modelling via PROAST software. Equipotent mixtures were designed and tested in all assays of the developed EuroMix *in vitro* toolbox. In the EuroMix approach, the default assumption is that the model of dose addition applies to all substances that cause the same adverse outcome, i.e. steatosis. This assumption could be confirmed for all substance tested so far in the AOP-wise *in vitro* assay toolbox.

Questions for clarification:

- Q** (Industry representative): When investigating possible deviations from dose addition, was bioavailability considered (e.g. via a PBPK model)?
- A** (EuroMix representative): This is an important consideration when interpreting the experimental results. Several groups with EuroMix had worked on PBK models, and most of them are implemented in the EuroMix model and data platform.

EuroMix test strategy: use of *in vitro* data to define the cumulative assessment group for cranio-facial malformation

Angelo Moretto, UMIL

EuroMix explored the possibilities and options that are available to carry out the risk assessment of combined exposures to substances that cause craniofacial malformations. While exposure considerations should take prominence in the identification of the compounds for which the combined assessment should be prioritized, for the purpose of EuroMix this part of the activity focused on the adverse outcome. Hazard identification and characterisation need to be put into an AOP to devise a strategy for both grouping compounds and testing mixtures. Also, it is essential to define the relative potency factor (RPF) and the capability of quantitative extrapolation of *in vitro* data (*in vitro in vivo* extrapolation, IVIVE) and the extrapolation from experimental animals to humans by means of Physiologically Based Toxicokinetics (PBPK). A tentative AOP has been developed based of imbalance of the retinoic acid pathway supported by *in silico* and *in vitro* tests, that included QSAR considerations and molecular docking, morphological observations and gene expression assays in the embryonic stem cell test, the rat whole embryo culture, and the zebrafish embryo (ZFE) toxicity assay. On the basis of the *in silico* and *in vitro* data the following compounds

were chosen for the in vivo study: cyproconazole, triadimefon (same molecular initiating event, MIE) and valproic acid (different MIE). The question that has been asked relates to the level of conservatism that is introduced by the inclusion in the cumulative assessment group of compounds with dissimilar MIE but same phenotypic adverse outcome and the application of the dose-additivity model.

Questions for clarification:

- Q** (Industry representative): Please explain the meaning of ‘dissimilar’ and ‘similar’ mode of action
- A** (EuroMix representative): Similar means the same molecular initiating event (MIE) is involved, whereas dissimilar means a different MIE, with reference to the AOP.
- Q** (Unidentified representative): How quantitative are AOPs, what is known about the doses triggering the next key-event in the AOP. Is there a threshold dose to trigger the effect and in the next key-event of the AOP?
- A** (EuroMix representative): This may depend on where we are on the dose-response curve. Perhaps we need another way of thinking about this rather than the just similar/dissimilar mode of action and how to add these up.
- Q** (Policy maker representative): Is there a plan to define a threshold at which the doses become additive?
- A** (EuroMix representative): This requires new testing. It was not done in the EuroMix project due to time constraints and the time needed for all the studies.

EuroMix test strategy: use of *in vitro* data to improve and/or complete hazard data collection for endocrine disruption

Toine Bovee, WUR

An adverse outcome pathway (AOP) is needed for both grouping and testing of compounds and mixtures thereof, as understanding the molecular initiating events (MIE), the key events (KE) and the KE relationships are especially fundamental when assessing combined exposure. In addition, it is essential to define the potency of each component (relative potency factor, RPF) which allows the appropriate weighing of each compound being assessed. This part of the EuroMix approach focusses on testing compounds and mixtures that cause endocrine effects, i.e. feminisation, by either targeting the estrogen receptor (ER) or androgen receptor (AR). It was shown that in-silico molecular docking can be applied qualitatively in first instance to predict the affinity of compounds to a specific receptor. Subsequently, in-vitro transcriptional activation (TA) assays were used to establish the ER and AR agonistic and antagonistic properties and the cognate RPFs. However, receptor docking, ER and AR TA assays do not allow determination of RPFs for compounds with a dissimilar mode of action (MoA). Therefore, the fish sexual development test (FSDT) was used to establish RPFs of compounds with a dissimilar MoA by examining the gonadal phenotype as an endpoint of ER and AR MIEs, and expression of vitellogenin in zebrafish liver as a marker of the MIE “ERalpha activation”. Testing of selected compounds and mixtures thereof in the rat development test is ongoing. Preliminary results are in line with the expected effects of flutamide regarding anogenital distance, nipple retention and cryptorchidism. In addition, marker genes for KEs in the ERalpha and/or AR part of the AOP network, were selected from literature. Testis tissue was collected for gene expression analysis (testing and analysis are ongoing).

Questions for clarification:

- Q** (Unidentified representative): At which time points were measurements made (for nipple retention effect)? What do you conclude about the sensitivity of the endpoints tested? [In studies referred to by the questioner, it was found that these were not so sensitive in males]
- A** (EuroMix representative): The measurements were made directly after birth. Nipple retention and anogenital distance measures were the most sensitive of the tests, also in literature (e.g. for flutamide and linuron).
- Q** (Unidentified representative): It is difficult to interpret results when multiple MOAs are considered. Some chemicals may have other MOAs that are not considered in the AOP, e.g. by the PR.
- A** (EuroMix representative): Good point, but the main point to emphasise is that we should not select for testing those chemicals that have already different MOAs by their selves. It is then impossible to determine the true effect. E.g., bisphenol A, this compound has already different MOAs by itself, i.e. it is at least an ER-agonist, AR-antagonist and it affects the steroidogenesis. Therefore, we tested many compounds and eventually selected flutamide and linuron as a pure AR-antagonists (both enough literature data, especially on flutamide), and dienestrol as an ER-agonist (but no data on dienestrol (human or animal)).
- Q** (Policy maker representative): What will be published? Although linuron showed no effect, this should still be published.
- A** (EuroMix representative): yes, all *in silico*, *in vitro* and *in vivo* data will be published, including the *in vivo* absence of effects by linuron in our experiments with fish and rat. However, mixture testing is on-going, and it is possible that linuron has an effect when combined with another compound. Thus, more than additive effect? if combination has effect with other compounds.

General discussion

(EuroMix representative): BPA is a kind of mixture within itself with dissimilar MOAs, possibly enhancing feminisation. Other compounds might also be self-mixtures with dissimilar MOAs but that cancel each other's effects regarding feminisation, e.g. phthalates, which are ER-antagonists and AR-antagonists. So, what can we do, given these findings and not get confused...the answer is to focus on the MOA, i.e. the MIE and key events that lead to the effect. However, also a focus such AOPs can lead to confusion, as it is hard to test or prove AOPs by epidemiological studies. In that regard, human patients would be perhaps the best option, as they are at least clearly treated with a bioactive compound at a high concentration, but also this will be difficult in real practice.

- Q** (Academic representative): How was the overall list of compounds selected? The contaminants in food did not include heavy metals? In organic farming metals like copper may be important.
- A** (EuroMix representative): Compounds were selected that were suitable for *in silico* testing, so metals were not included, even though they could be important components of dietary exposure.
- A** (EuroMix representative): In the US there is an ongoing assessment of combinations of metals in the diet. Some metals are essential (e.g. manganese, iron) and some are non-

essential (e.g. cadmium), posing only a toxicological risk, which can complicate such an assessment.

- Q** (Unidentified representative): Were compounds selected based on exposure? What were the reasons for selection, and what databases were used? How can compounds be prioritised for co-exposure?
- A** (EuroMix representative): Exposures were estimated using dietary consumption data combined with pesticide monitoring/occurrence data. Where possible, the compounds were those to which there was the highest exposure. However, these were not always the most appropriate for the AOP-testing proposed, and so some alternatives were used, based on a combination of AOP and/or exposure.
- A** (EuroMix representative): Some compounds might be omitted because their exposure levels are so low.
- A** (EuroMix representative): Compounds were selected for two major important reasons: 1) purely from the MOA – *in vitro* data, i.e. selecting pure ER-agonists and pure AR-antagonists if; 2) otherwise exposure driven, therefore we selected linuron, it is a compound to which consumers are exposed to and it is epidemiological related to decrease the anogenital distance and *in vitro* linuron was characterised as a pure AR-antagonist. In some cases, exposure and *in vitro* selected compounds (dimethoate, deltamethrin and 8-prenylnaringenin) could not be used for practical reasons, e.g. rat did not like the custard containing the compound or the compound is too expensive.

Harmonisation and Usability of the EuroMix tools

Overall chair: *Anton Riteveld, RIVM*

Overall rapporteur: *Helga Gunnlaugsdóttir, MATIS*

Session 1

Rapporteurs: *Sophie Jensen, MATIS and Jens Schubert, BfR*

Welcome and workshop objectives

Jacob van Klaveren, RIVM

No clarification questions

Comparison between in vitro and in vivo experiments and the role of PB-PK models to extrapolate in vitro data collection for use in human risk assessment

Angelo Moretto, UMIL

Risk assessment of combined exposures to chemicals requires potency normalised exposure information. Depending on whether exposures are available as external (e.g.: oral intake) or internal (e.g. at the molecular target or a surrogate such as plasma), relative potency (RPF) of compounds to be applied may vary. In the case of external exposure, the RPF can be derived from in vivo dose-response data and the values take into account both the difference in ADME and the different potency at the target. RPFs are then derived on the basis of the NOAEL or the BMD_x of each compound relative to the index compound (IC). Generally, data are available only in animals and, therefore, differences in ADME and in sensitivity of the target need to be taken into account. ADME can be compared by use of PBPK modelling which can be informed also by data in humans, if available; differences in sensitivity might be identified by use of in vitro (or in silico) data that quantitatively assess the MIE and/or certain KE in the AOP, if known. On the other hand, RPFs can be based on data from in vitro assays which provide values of potency at-the-target in animals and, preferably, in humans. In this case, derived RPFs only consider the interaction with the target and ADME is not involved. Therefore, the comparator will be the internal dose at-the-target or, as a surrogate, in a biological fluid (generally the plasma). Also, such at-the-target RPFs may be used when only external exposure data are available with the application of specific PBPK models.

Questions for clarification:

- Q** (Industry representative): 1. The idea of threshold, can it be described by quantitative AOP? How to deal with different AO? 2. Dose addition in malformation?
- A** (EuroMix representative): 1. This is a key point - is we believe in threshold. When do different pathways give you an outcome and we can measure the sum of this? 2. One criterium is timing, since cranial malformation has a very narrow window => in this case it is very likely that Valproic acid imbalance is the reason for the malformation. However, mechanistic information is required.

How the EuroMix concept and tools can contribute to international harmonisation

Alan Boobis, ICL

In general, there is appreciable alignment of the principles for assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals by EFSA, EPA and other organisations. These all emphasise the importance of problem formulation, including specification of the objectives and acceptable degree of uncertainty for assessment, the basis for grouping chemicals and the choice of assessment approach. There is also general agreement on the need for tiered approaches for both hazard and exposure assessment, to avoid being overly conservative. The use of mode of action information in refining assessment groups has also been broadly incorporated, as has been transparent delineation of uncertainties at each tier. In a number of chemical sectors, there is common application of these principles. However, in the area of pesticides, there are significant differences between the proposed approach in Europe and that which is in use in the USA.

The EuroMix toolbox has potential application, regardless of the approach used, in different sectors or geographical regions, for both data rich and data poor chemicals. Whilst harmonisation of the specific risk assessment methodology might not be possible, at least in the short term, the EuroMix toolbox can contribute to harmonisation of the principles used, in addressing the above issues, the standard of reporting and data templates. The EuroMix Handbook will seek to provide best practice for the range of problem formulations that might concern risk managers and will encourage further harmonisation, to the extent possible.

Questions for clarification:

- Q** (EuroMix representative): Agree with AOP, for antibiotics (e.g. trimethoprim) we have examples where there is more than dose addition => must be something else.
- A** (EuroMix representative): There are situations where you have to worry about synergistic effects but in some cases, there are no such worries. I am not saying that synergistic effects never occur, however this is very unlikely at human relevant exposure doses. Nonetheless frameworks should allow considering also synergistic effects.

How the EuroMix concept and tools can be used in line with OECD and EFSA guidance

Johanna Zilliacus, KI

The EuroMix concept, methodology and tools for assessing risks of combined exposures to multiple substances are described in the EuroMix handbook for mixture risk assessment. The handbook is consistent with and expands upon the recent documents on mixture risk assessment published by OECD and EFSA. The aim is to provide a practical handbook for harmonised application of the EuroMix outcome under consideration of EFSA and OECD guidance.

The handbook contains concise descriptions of the EuroMix methodology and tools with reference to the EuroMix toolbox. The EuroMix toolbox is a web-based platform where toxicity and exposure data can be uploaded, and mixture risk assessment can be performed. Annexes in the handbook provide detailed information or useful templates. Illustrative examples are also included as annexes.

The EuroMix approach for mixture risk assessment is component-based, tiered and very flexible, enabling assessment of both data-rich and data-poor substances. Substances are grouped based on toxicological considerations in assessment groups. Grouping based on other characteristics can also be applied in the EuroMix toolbox. Toxicity and exposure information for each substance in the assessment group is used for estimation of the combined risk using the dose-addition hypothesis and

relative potency factors approach. The refined hazard characterisation approach is based on benchmark dose modelling and physiologically based kinetic modelling. The concept of adverse outcome pathways forms the basis for the toxicological considerations for grouping as well as for the identification of endpoints that can be measured or predicted to derive toxicity data and relative potency factors. The adverse outcome pathway approach supports the use of *in vitro* data in a tiered testing strategy. *In silico* modelling can be used for grouping and for setting test priorities. The dietary exposure assessment of mixtures is based on probabilistic methodology considering the individual consumption and concentration data and allowing estimation of different percentiles of exposure to the mixture. Aggregate exposure assessment of other exposure routes is also described. The EuroMix handbook and toolbox provide practical support to apply the OECD and EFSA guidance on mixture risk assessment.

Questions for clarification:

Q (Industry representative): This is good development in *in vitro*. In the future do you think you can shorten the time by using the available *in vivo* data. Toxicity and PK data could be helpful.

A (EuroMix representative): I agree, we should take advantage of all available data and find ways of doing that.

Session 2

Rapporteurs: *Johanna Zilliacus, KI and Helene Deruwe, Freshfel*

WHO/FAO consultation workshop on combined exposure to multiple chemicals

Amelie Crepet, ANSES

According to the EUROMIX proposal, FAO and WHO organized an expert Consultation to take place in WHO HQ - Geneva on 15 to 18 April 2019. The goal of the meeting is to verify that the new strategy and tools developed by EUROMIX are accessible for developing countries and emerging economies and cannot be seen as undue barriers to food trade.

A call for experts was published (https://www.who.int/foodsafety/Call_for_experts-final_2.pdf) and 14 experts applied including 7 experts from non-EU Countries. WHO proceeded with an internal and external review of the application and checked for possible conflicts of interest. The expert consultation will involve 12 experts including 4 experts from non-EU countries (Australia, Brazil, Canada and China). Experts will be invited in their personal capacity on the basis of their expert knowledge and they will not represent any institution or employer.

The report of the Consultation should be posted on the WHO web-site soon after the meeting for public consultation before publication.

Questions for clarification:

Q (Academic representative): Who will be present from the EuroMix consortium?

A (EuroMix representative): Alan Boobis, Amelie Crepet, Nathalie Gotz, Jacob van Klaveren, Angelo Moretto

- Q** (Academic representative): Imazalil and thiacloprid are very rich on data on exposure. There is a lot of data available for pesticides, but there is also a lot of missing data in the monitoring. These missing data are very strategic to manage the risk assessment, and they change the results on exposure. This should be discussed in the exposure assessment.
- A** (EuroMix representative): Acknowledgment of the data gaps. The good thing of the tools is that we can also identify these gaps, and that there are procedures to fill in those gaps. Through the identification, there will be an indication of where to go, where efforts need to be bundled.

How the EuroMix concept and toolbox can be used in line with JRC strategy (e.g. IPCHEM connection, JRC vision documents)

Stephanie Bopp, JRC

The European Commission has worked in the area of chemical mixtures over the last decade (The State-of-the-Art report on Chemical Mixtures (2009), the Opinion of the non-food Scientific Committees (2011) and the Commission Communication on Chemical Mixtures (2012)). JRC started in 2014 to review regulatory requirements in EU chemical legislation and related guidance documents, looked into available scientific methodologies and lessons learned from case studies of mixture risk assessment.

Since it is practically impossible to test all possible mixtures experimentally, smart strategies are needed to assess the potential hazards using new tools that rely less on animal testing and incorporate instead alternative experimental and computational tools. Novel, non-animal tools and scientific methodologies show high potential for the assessment of combined effects of chemicals on humans and the environment. They allow meaningful information on individual mixture components or whole mixtures to be derived, enabling a better understanding of the underlying mechanisms of their effects. Their main strengths lie in their integrated use and putting into context different aspects of the hazard from combined exposure to multiple chemicals.

From this perspective, we will look into the findings and toolbox developed in the EuroMix project.

No clarification questions

EFSA Risk Assessment Agenda and how the EuroMix concept and tools can be used in cooperation with the member states

Jean-Lou Dorne, EFSA

The European Union Risk Assessment Agenda is a collaborative initiative coordinated by EFSA together with national food safety agencies. It aims to prioritise research and risk assessment activities that are new or not (fully) covered by other programmes with a focus on promoting partnering at national, EU and international scale. Currently, an annual exercise is performed by EFSA jointly with Member States to take stock of the implementation and submission of existing and new project ideas under the current Delphi priorities. EFSA will establish a database to collate all available information and facilitate networking and partnering of organisations across the EU.

In this context, risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals “chemical mixtures” has been identified as a priority topic for EFSA and Member states. In February 2019, the scientific

Committee of EFSA has adopted, after public consultation, a harmonised guidance document on risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals for human health, animal health and ecological risk assessment. EFSA will implement the guidance to further support risk assessment in this area for regulated compounds such as pesticides and feed additives as well as contaminants. The EUROMIX project has been exploring new testing approaches and developed a set of tools to support risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals in the human health area. The possible next steps on how EFSA will consider the EUROMIX toolbox in cooperation with Member States are discussed.

Questions for clarification:

- Q** (Unidentified representative): Will the EFSA guidance document be used across the groups of substances, e.g. pesticides and contaminants?
- A** (EFSA representative): In case such a question will come from the risk managers, it can be used.
- Q** (EuroMix representative): How will EFSA organise the process to link all the models together? Is EFSA open for more organised collaboration and making things functional?
- A** (EFSA representative): New version of the Open FoodTox includes more properties of the substances. Summary of exposure data is also included. Use of OECD template highlights the transparency of the approaches that are used. EFSA is updating with JRC the mechanistic template to report intermediary data. MIEs will be able to be structured within this template. Link the database to a set of QSAR models. Development of a web-based app to input exposure data to run a model for different types of questionnaires. Input can be used for the human model. All the above offer a lot of opportunities.

How the web-based EuroMix tools can be used to refine risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple pesticides

Stephanie Melching-Kollmuss, BASF

Cumulative risk assessment will be implemented in the data requirements of pesticides in relation to MRLs (396/2005) and approval of active ingredients (1107/2009) once regulatory-acceptable methods are available. The cumulative assessment groups (CAG) so far published by EFSA contain up to 127 substances in one group based on similar effects on the same target organ. Preliminary deterministic cumulative risk assessments conducted by ECPA identified risk drivers, the need for more realistic exposure scenarios, and further refinements. For hazard-based refinements ECPA proposed a decision tree approach which follows strict adversity and human relevance criteria, and the Lead Effect concept (consider only substances for grouping whose lowest NOAEL is based on target organ toxicity). Tools developed by the EuroMix Project could be used in the future to apply refinements to assessments of exposure (e.g. processing factors or likelihood of co-exposure) and hazard (i.e. uploading additional comparative toxicological information: relative potency factors using QSARs or in vitro experiments or on kinetics/bioavailability).

However, further experience with the model can only be gained, if full access to the model and the underlying monitoring and consumption data is granted, and more experience in filling data templates for uploading into the system is gained by e.g. exchanging views in multidisciplinary user groups bringing together authority, academia and industry scientists.

Questions for clarification:

- Q** (EuroMix representative): Re. the availability of data for consumption in databases: what do you identify to be the main problem here?
- A** (Industry representative): There is no access to detailed data for all the countries in the EFSA database.
- A** (EFSA representative): New data requirement comparing the human metabolism with the rat metabolism. The generation of isoform specific data for humans and rats is needed.
- A** (Industry representative): Yes kinetic data is used.

General discussion

- Q** (EuroMix representative): It is suggested to decrease the size of assessment groups. EFSA has addressed the uncertainty of the groups. In the EuroMix model and data platform this uncertainty can be included in the probabilistic model. Therefore, the use of this new approach makes it less important to reduce the size of assessment groups.
- A** (Industry representative): As we have never applied probabilistic approach on hazard endpoints, we don't know how it will look like. How to apply weight of evidence, how to decide what to not to group at all.
- A** (EuroMix representative): there are 2 issues: 1) criteria established by which EFSA selected compounds which should be considered to be part of a group. But do all compounds that are in the group meet the criteria? There is a concern that they don't all do it. Then why not include every compound? Only a % of actors that were looked at were included, because they gave signals. But were those signals real? 2) Should we have large groups? When doing cross-sectorial assessment, there is a need. But this is a reflection of needs of risk managers, who don't all want huge groups. Hence, there is scope for both approaches in the EuroMix model and data platform.
- A** (Industry representative): there are some detailed errors that can be identified, but weight of evidence should be taken into account whether it belongs to that group.
- Q** (EFSA representative): When you use benchmark modelling, do you use a default value for a benchmark response?
- A** (EuroMix representative): In the toolbox you can specify whatever benchmark response you would like to use.
- Q** (OECD representative): for further disseminating the outcomes: 1) Re. work done on AOPs: Any AOPs that were developed could be entered to the AOP wiki, an open source platform 2) Pilots with Vega. By summer, the extension repository where everybody can put their QSAR tool will be ready 3) OECD harmonised templates on how to report data of test guidelines to record the toxicity of exposure in order to communicate information between databases. This will create a global setting of how data can be shared between different jurisdictions.

- A** (EuroMix representative): The EuroMix consortium carefully aligned the EuroMix model and data platform to international databases and systems. Therefore, close collaboration with EFSA is key.
- Q** (Unidentified representative): Exposure to mixtures happens in real life. We shouldn't just put protection on the chemicals, but also protection of consumers is needed, and not just on chemicals of pesticides. The models are simple and are good to start with, because mixtures need to be taken into account. But political decisions are needed for humans to be safe, and there is still a long way to go. Adding an extra safety factor of at least 10 would be a first step.
- A** (EuroMix representative): EuroMix tried to cover a broader perspective of chemicals than pesticides only.
- A** (Hidde Rang, VWS): A lot of chemicals can be hazardous, we know there is a cumulative effect, but we're only at the beginning. There is a lot of knowledge about pesticides and the amount that is present in food and people are exposed to. First task is focus on pesticides. Other contaminants or compounds can be added to the calculation, but you need to start somewhere. An extra safety factor wouldn't change the situation. People would get more worried about exposure, but there would be no change to the situation in which people are exposed to contaminants.
- Q** (NGO representative): Are synergistic effects of azole fungicides possible?
- A** (EuroMix representative): Available experimental data suggests not in mammals at the human relevant exposure levels. There are exceptions possible at higher dose testing in animals, but we need a clearer framework to identify the exceptions
- A** (EuroMix representative): Using EuroMix mixture testing deviations from dose addition can be identified
- A** (JRC representative): We need a system to filter out when not relevant. A systematic review on synergism is currently being organised, probably ready by mid-August
- A** (EFSA representative): For bees, evidence for synergies
- Q** (Academic representative): 1) When will the next version of the software be available? 2) How to prioritise assessment groups for testing? What are the next steps?
- A** (EuroMix representative): Re. the software: EuroMix ends 15/5/2019. There will be a beta version ready by the end of the project, and this will be proposed to the risk assessors to use themselves. The handbook will be available too. Based on agreements data will be available. An implementation plan will be prepared.
- A** (EFSA representative): Re. Prioritisation regarding new assessment groups for pesticides is to be decided by EFSA pesticide Unit.
- A** (EuroMix representative): Re. Prioritisation: Introduction of the assessment groups for pesticides over the next 2 years. The question on how and what to prioritise is for EFSA and EC to be answered. Usually they prioritise the biggest sub-groups.
- A** (Industry representative): EFSA has suggested priorities for the neurotoxic assessment groups.

- Q** (NGO representative): Cumulative risk assessment is something the law demands in order to better assess the risks of mixtures of chemicals. In the previous session, it was said that cumulative risk assessment shouldn't be a trade barrier and that this will be discussed in Geneva. In EU legislation, it is said that health and the environmental standards should take priority over trade. What is the legal basis for the cumulative risk assessment not to be trade barriers? What is EuroMix's role in the discussions?
- A** (EuroMix representative): Risk assessment should be based on science. We have to protect the consumer. This is a policy issue number one. In Geneva in April 2019, there will be two meetings: 1) 4th Harmonisation Workshop, an information gathering exercise 2) WHO-consultation meeting to develop an approach for cumulative risk assessment that doesn't exist at the moment within the Codex Alimentarius. The Codex Alimentarius is not bound by European legislation, it's bound by World Trade Organisations (WTO) and standards set by the Codex Play a role in trade conflicts. However, the starting point for standards is science and therefore there will be a discussion at the WHO, which might lead to a guidance document, which will be put to consultation before publication. EuroMix experts will advise the Codex Alimentarius in their capacity as selected independent experts.
- A** (EuroMix representative): The level of protection and how combined exposure or risk assessment should be performed is a political decisions are consequently, these decisions should eb made by policy makers
- A** (EuroMix representative): There are three assays for the same endpoints. Every assay cannot be assessed on its own, the combination of the assays is more important. Embryotic stem cell tests can be used for dose additivity or synergism, the other 2 assays can be used to set MRLs. Every assay has its own advantages and disadvantages, but they could be used for different things. Some assays are not suitable to test mixtures.
- A** (EuroMix representative): Development of a framework to establish the fitness of purpose is being worked out in another project. Some methods will have their own roles.

Appendix 1.

Program from the EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix joint stakeholder workshop, *The Chemical Cocktail Challenge*, held 26 March 2019

AND

Program from the project specific EuroMix stakeholder workshop, *Harmonisation and Usability of the EuroMix tools*, held 27 March 2019

The Chemical Cocktail Challenge

March 26th 2019

“A workshop on results and conclusions from the two H2020-funded projects, EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix, and their implications for future needs for chemical mixture risk assessment”

AIM OF THE STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP:

The workshop is aimed at gathering key scientists, researchers, policy makers, and stakeholders from authorities, industry and civil society. Both projects, EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix, will present key results and demonstrate new tools and approaches for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals (mixtures) and how these could benefit future European food and chemical safety policy.

ORGANISING COMMITTEE:

EDC-MixRisk:

Åke Bergman, Karolinska Institutet (SE)
Joelle Rüegg, Karolinska Institutet (SE)
Elina Drakvik, Karolinska Institutet (SE)

EuroMix:

Jacob van Klaveren, National Institute Public Health and the Environment (RIVM, NL)
Helene Deruwe, Freshfel Europe (BE)
Sophie Jensen, Matis (IS)
Helga Gunnlaugsdóttir, Matis (IS)

VENUE:

Thon Hotel EU
Rue de La Loi 75,
1040 Brussels

www.thonhotels.com/eu

ABSTRACTS:

The abstracts from the speakers will be available at the project websites **EDC-MixRisk**: <https://edcmixrisk.ki.se/> & **EuroMix**: <http://www.euromixproject.eu/>

The Chemical Cocktail Challenge

March 26th 2019

“A workshop on results and conclusions from the two H2020-funded projects, EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix, and their implications for future needs for chemical mixture risk assessment”

Programme for 26 March 2019, Thon Hotel, Brussels

The morning part of the stakeholder workshop will focus on presenting and discussing the key results of both projects and stakeholder perspectives in a joint plenary, whereas the afternoon sessions will showcase and discuss the new approaches and tools project-specifically.

Overall Chairs: *Gregory Moore, Keml & Charles Wijker, Ministry Health, Welfare and Sport* Overall Rapporteurs: *Helga Gunnlaugsdóttir, Matis & Elina Drakvik, KI*

Time

8:00-9:00 Registration and welcome coffee

SESSION 1: Joint forces tackling chemical mixtures - Key results and conclusions from EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix

Rapporteurs: *Sophie Jensen and Mattias Öberg*

Time

Title / Speaker

9:00-9:05 Welcome from the project coordinator(s) and aims of the workshop, *Åke Bergman, KI; Jacob v. Klaveren, RIVM*
9:05-9:15 Mixtures and food safety, *Sabine Julicher, Director, Food and Feed Safety, Innovation, DG Sante, EC*
9:15-9:25 How research contributes to solving the mixture challenge, *Maria Pilar Aguar Fernandez, Head of Unit, DG RTD, EC*
9:25-10:05 EuroMix highlights and key recommendations, *Jacob v. Klaveren, RIVM; Alfonso Lampen, BfR; Hilko van der Voet, WUR*
10:05-10:45 EDC-MixRisk highlights and key messages, *Åke Bergman, KI; Carl-Gustaf Bornehag, KU; Joëlle Rüegg, KI; Chris Gennings, ICAHN*
10:45-11:10 **Coffee Break**

SESSION 2: Stakeholder perspectives on EDC-MixRisk and EuroMix implications for the future

Rapporteurs: *Helene Deruwe and Elina Drakvik*

Time

Title / Speaker

11:10-11:25 EFSA's perspective, *Jean-Lou Dorne, EFSA*
11:25-11:40 OECD's perspective, *Eeva Leinala, OECD*
11:40-11:55 ChemTrust's perspective, *Ninja Reineke, ChemTrust*
11:55-12:10 Industry perspective, *Steffen Schneider, BASF*
12:10-12:25 Perspectives from three European Commission's DG's, *Laura Fabrizi, DG SANTE; Peter Korytar, DG ENV; Stephanie Bopp, DG JRC*
12:25-12:55 Open discussion
12:55-13:00 Word of thanks & practical information for the parallel sessions in the afternoon
13:00-14:00 **Lunch**

Two Parallel Afternoon Sessions in Separate Rooms:

EuroMix session A – Room Belgium II: Applications of the EuroMix toolbox for improving exposure assessment of mixtures Chair: <i>Mirjam Luijten</i> Rapporteur: <i>Sophie Jensen</i>		EDC-MixRisk session B – Room Belgium III: EDC-MixRisk approach: Case study of mixture effects on sexual development Chair: <i>Joëlle Rüegg</i> Rapporteur: <i>Elina Drakvik</i>	
Title / Speaker Exposure assessment overarching sectors and tools to identify mixtures of concern <i>Amelie Crepet, ANSES</i>	Time 14:00-14:20	Title / Speaker EDC-MixRisk study design and epidemiological evidence – results from the SELMA study <i>Carl-Gustaf Bornehag, KAU</i>	
Aggregated exposure assessment <i>Marc Kennedy, FERA</i>	14:20-14:40	Mixture effects in a mouse model <i>Efthymia Kitraki, UOA</i>	
Human study and how to compare real life exposure with predicted exposure using the EuroMix concept and tools <i>Trine Husøy, NIPH</i>	14:40-15:00	New risk assessment strategy – Similar Mixtures Approach <i>Chris Gennings, ICAHN</i>	
Joint coffee break	15:00-15:20	Joint coffee break	

Two Parallel Afternoon Sessions in Separate Rooms:

EuroMix session C – Room Belgium II: Applications of the EuroMix toolbox for improving hazard assessment of mixtures Chair: <i>Alan Boobis</i> Rapporteur: <i>Marc Kennedy</i>		EDC-MixRisk session D – Room Belgium III: From science towards regulation - EDC-MixRisk approaches for better risk assessment and management of mixtures Chair: <i>Mattias Öberg</i> Rapporteur: <i>Elina Drakvik</i>	
Title / Speaker Lower tier assessment using <i>in silico</i> approaches <i>Ad Peijnenburg, WUR</i>	Time 15:20-15:40	Title / Speaker Systematic integration of epidemiological and experimental evidence into mixture risk assessment strategies <i>Giuseppe Testa, IEO</i>	
EuroMix test strategy: use of <i>in vitro</i> data to improve and/or complete hazard data collection for chemicals relevant for cumulative effect on AOP liver steatosis <i>Alfonso Lampen, BfR</i>	15:40-16:00	Taking into account environmental mixtures in risk assessment: new Acceptable Concentration Range (ACR) models <i>Chris Gennings, ICAHN</i>	
EuroMix test strategy: use of <i>in vitro</i> data to define the cumulative assessment group for cranio-facial malformation <i>Angelo Moretto, UMIL</i>	16:00-16:20	Application of systematic review and integrated assessment (SYRINA) framework to mixtures <i>Thuy Bui, SU</i>	
EuroMix test strategy: use of <i>in vitro</i> data to improve and/or complete hazard data collection for endocrine disruption <i>Toine Bovee, WUR</i>	16:20-16:40	Recommendations and options for better risk assessment and management of mixtures <i>Christina Rudén, SU</i>	
General discussion	16:40-17:15	General discussion	
Joint dinner at the Atelier 29	18:00	Joint dinner at the Atelier 29	

EuroMix Stakeholder Workshop
Harmonisation and Usability of the EuroMix tools

March 27th 2019

The aim of the workshop is to present the EuroMix AOP-wise test strategy and test results, the EuroMix model and data platform, discuss how the results can be used internationally as well as for follow-up activities on combined exposure assessment to multiple chemicals.

Programme for 27 March 2019, Thon Hotel, Brussels

Overall Chair: *Anton Rietveld, RIVM*
 Overall Rapporteur: *Helga Gunnlaugsdóttir, Matís*

8:30-9:00	Registration and welcome coffee
Session 1 Rapporteurs: <i>Jens Schubert & Sophie Jensen</i>	
9:00-9:10	Welcome and workshop objectives <i>Jacob van Klaveren, RIVM</i>
9:10-9:30	Comparison between in vitro and in vivo experiments and the role of PB-PK models to extrapolate in vitro data collection for use in human risk assessment <i>Angelo Moretto, UMIL</i>
9:30-9:50	How the EuroMix concept and tools can contribute to international harmonisation <i>Alan Boobis, ICL</i>
9:50-10:10	How the EuroMix concept and tools can be used in line with OECD and EFSA guidance <i>Johanna Zilliacus, KI</i>
10:10-10:30	Coffee Break
Session 2 Rapporteurs: <i>Johanna Zilliacus & Helene Deruwe</i>	
10:30-10:40	WHO/FAO consultation workshop on combined exposure to multiple chemicals <i>Amelie Crepet, ANSES</i>
10:40-11:00	How the EuroMix concept and toolbox can be used in line with JRC strategy (e.g. IPCHEM connection, JRC vision documents) <i>Stephanie Bopp, DG JRC</i>
11:00-11:20	EFSA Risk Assessment Agenda and how the EuroMix concept and tools can be used in cooperation with the member states <i>Jean-Lou Dorne, EFSA</i>
11:20-11:40	How the web-based EuroMix tools can be used to refine risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple pesticides <i>Stephanie Melching-Kollmuss, BASF</i>
11:40-12:20	General Discussion
12:20-12:30	Concluding remarks
12:30-14:00	Lunch

